

DIDACTIC IDEAS AND PEDAGOGICAL CONCEPTS IN THE PARABLES OF XF C. GELLERT

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Abstract : This in the article Didactic ideas and pedagogical concepts in the parables of XF C. Gellert about written of C. Gellert " Parable and of the collection of stories " (" Fabeln und Erzählungen "). himself of the author classic meaning in the form of parable from the text moving away and allegorical in the form of short instructive poetic parable genre is approaching shows.

Keywords: parable, pedagogical concepts, German, fable, chronological correspondence.

The didactic ideas and pedagogical concepts in the parables of X.F.C.Gellert, a famous parable writer, a prominent figure of the early Enlightenment period, occupy an important place in the development of not only German, but also world parables. It is also expressed in the parables of his moral lectures, which he studied at the University of Leipzig and published as a separate work. C. Gellert's lectures on moral philosophy included the topics of raising children, family relations, issues of faith and religion, and moral problems. At the same time, the practice of reinterpreting ancient fables in new ways, whether in cinematic format or otherwise, without relying on their original source material, often undermines the social hierarchies inherent in Eurocentric classical fables. put forward the idea that the traditional values recognized as universal for the reader can lead to a change in his mind. For example, C. Gellert's pedagogical views, which have a solid theoretical basis, are fully reflected in his moral lecture number XVIII. The basis of these ideas is expressed in the parable "Monkeys and Bears" ("Die Affen die Bären"). In traditional fables, bears are greedy characters who are clumsy and slow-moving. But for C. Gellert, bears are intelligent, natural creatures that raise their children according to the laws of nature, monkeys are a symbol of the upper class with all the negative qualities of that time. According to the parable, the monkeys ask the bear for advice on how to raise healthy and strong children, that bears treat their children gently, that they (bears) find their children in difficulties, that as soon as their children stand on their feet, even in the heat, They say that even in the cold, they walk with them in the forests and fields. One of the main ideas of

both the above lecture and the parable is that the closer a person is to nature, the more integrated and harmonious his personality will be.

In this matter, the German author JJ Rousseau (1712-1778) in his novel "Emile" (1762) is close to the theory of "Education of the Perfect Man". As for the chronological correspondence, the parables of C. Gellert appeared many years before the above-mentioned work of the French writer. At the same time, it is wrong to talk about the compatibility of other views of C. Gellert and Rousseau. In the lectures of the German author, there is only one mention of Rousseau's views, and even then it is accompanied by criticism.

C. Gellert's allegorical work is a theater genre "larmoyante comedy" created by the French Philippe Detouche (1680-1754) and Pierre de Lacosset (1680-1754). closely related to "comédie larmoyante", 1692-1754). C. Gellert's parables "Beshiktebratar" ("Gottesanbeterin") and "The Sick Wife" ("Die kranke Frau") and the comedy "The Lovely Sisters" ("Die Zärtlichen Schwester") C. Gellert's moral philosophy education through parables uses the method. C. Gellert learns the tradition of introducing the parable into the context of the work from the founder of sentimentalism, the English writer S. Richardson. The English writer used a number of proverbs and sayings in his novel "Pamela" (1740). C. Gellert highly appreciates Richardson's work, and in turn, confirms the influence of the English writer on C. Gellert's work.

Independent works as of C. Gellert parables 1741 in Germany - in "Belustigungen des Verstandes und des Witzes" in the magazine publication done. March of 1745 in the month "Proverbs and stories" complete work of the collection in 1748 second Vol publication done. In 1744 C. Gellert Latin in the language parable genre to poetics about "De poesie apologorum eorumque scriptoribus" scientific work publication did and Leipzig at the university professorship title took. In 1772 this work German into the language "Proverbs and their authors about" ("Von denen Fabeln und deren Verfassern") name with translation done of C. Gellert parable and proverbs writing and their publication reach literary scholars by German in literature wide spread "proverb as an epidemic" ("Fabelepidemie") be described. This at the time from C. Gellert except in Germany Friedrich Hagedorn (1708-1754), Johann Wilhelm Ludwig Gleim (1719-1803), Johann -Christoph Gottsched (1700-1766), Karl Christian Gertner (1712-1791), Karl Gottlob Kramer (1758-1817), Gottold Ephraim G. Lessing (1729-1781) this in the genre creativity they did. Parable country in literature social turning face giving, of the authorities old political system failed happening and that's it with together, society new system Create

for yet too enough to potential and own instead of have didn't happen at the time important place catch starts of C. Gellert famous publications in Germany exactly short peace to the period right will come , i.e second Silesia war from the end after and seven yearly war from the beginning before wounded . That's it attention worthy of C. Gellert himself too own to work critical in relation has been and known time after the parables again worked _ Often it is long issues again edit did and original copies significant level shortened . B is his classic to the model , i.e compact to be take came In 1756 his " Some of parables criticism " (" Beurteilung einiger Fabeln aus der Belustigung ") title under article publication done This with german writer his own first his works publication reached " Belustigungen des Verstandes und des Witzes " magazine to the publication hint does of C. Gellert "Parable and of the collection of stories " (" Fabeln und Erzählungen "). himself of the author classic meaning in the form of parable from the text moving away and allegorical in the form of short instructive poetic parable genre approaching shows . German the author this two literary form separate does not show , that's it despite , the writer in his work this differences our observation can C. Gellert of parables from the story contribution (moral) in it generalized and expanded with classic from parables difference does Narratives from the story contribution (moral) worldly of life wisdom represents parable - everyday life philosophy philosophical - religious issues are also high speech style to himself feature with separate stands C. Gellert proverbs most of the time straight away instruction for uses , so for the plot not complicated , sometimes while sure instructions giving explains . In the example the writer this from the method does not use because this genre indirectly if also , teaching and of education hidden method is considered In the story in it movement participants people the fact that guess is done , for example while traditional respectively an allegory principle is used and an animal characters a person from the character come comes out

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